

ULTRASONICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NANOCLAY/POLY(ETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE) COMPOSITES

Kazuaki Sanada¹, Makoto Kawagoe¹ and Wataru Mizuno²

¹Department of Mechanical Systems Engineering, Toyama Prefectural University
5180 Kurokawa, Imizu, Toyama 939-0398, Japan
Email: sanada@pu-toyama.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.pu-toyama.ac.jp>

²Planning and Management Department, Toyama Industrial Technology Center
150 Futagamimachi, Takaoka, Toyama 933-0981, Japan
Email: mizuno@itc.pref.toyama.jp, web page: <http://www.itc.pref.toyama.jp>

Keywords: Nanoclay/polymer composites, Ultrasonication, Dynamic viscoelastic testing, Finite element analysis, Mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties of nanoclay/poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) composites have been investigated experimentally and analytically. The nanoclays were ultrasonicated in solvent and were dried in an oven. Specimens of PET composites with ultrasonicated nanoclays were then fabricated by melt processing. Dynamic viscoelastic tests were carried out and the effects of ultrasonication time and nanoclay volume fraction on the temperature dependence of the storage and loss moduli of the composites were discussed. The nanoclay dispersion in the PET matrix and the morphology of ultrasonicated nanoclays was also examined using a transmission electron microscope (TEM) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM). In addition to conducting experiments, finite element analyses were performed using a three-dimensional unit cell model to predict the elastic properties of nanoclay/PET composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Poly (ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is a low-cost, high-performance polymer that finds use in a wide variety applications including food and beverage packaging, textiles and automotive components. To enhance the mechanical properties of PET, the use of organomodified montmorillonite (nanoclay) as a reinforcement material has attracted significant attention. The nanoclays were expandable-layered silicates and can be intercalated and exfoliated into polymers. Better dispersion and high degree of intercalation and exfoliation of the nanoclays in the PET matrix lead to improve the mechanical properties of nanoclay/PET composites.

A melt processing is a more industrially viable route to the creation of polymeric nanocomposites. Many attempts have been reported recently on studying the morphology and properties of nanoclay/PET composites produced via melt processing. Solis et al. [1] investigated the effect of nanoclay content on the thermal, mechanical and rheological properties of nanoclay/PET composites produced via melt extrusion. Barber et al. [2] prepared nanoclay/PET composites via melt extrusion and discussed the effect of PET ionomer content on the mechanical properties of the composites. Ammala et al. [3] synthesized PET/nanoclay composites using two different types of nanoclays via melt extrusion and examined the dispersion of the nanoclays in the PET matrix. However, the synthesis of nanoclay/PET composites has not been as successful as compared with other polymers.

In recent years, the ultrasonication is being used in assistance of the dispersion, intercalation and exfoliation of the nanoclays. McAdam et al. [4] examined the effect of nanoclay content on the rheological and dynamic viscoelastic properties of nylon6/nanoclay composites prepared by ultrasonication and in situ polymerization. Tarawneh et al. [5] studied the effect of ultrasonication time on the dynamic viscoelastic properties of thermoplastic natural rubber/nanoclay composites.

The objective of this study is to prepare nanoclay/PET composites via ultrasonication and melt processing, and to examine the effects of ultrasonication time and nanoclay volume fraction on the temperature dependence of the dynamic viscoelastic properties of nanoclay/PET composites. A transmission electron microscope (TEM) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) were also used to observe the nanoclay dispersion in the PET matrix and the morphology of ultrasonicated nanoclays. Additionally, finite element analyses were employed to study the effects of thickness and volume fraction of nanoclays on the elastic properties of the nanoclay/PET composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and specimen preparation

The PET pellets of EFG70 from Bell Polyester Products were used as the matrix. The density of EFG70 is 1.34 g/cm³. Two types of nanoclays (DELLITE 43B from Laviosa Chimica Mineraria and Cloisite 10A from Rock Wood Holdings) were also used as the reinforcement. Table 1 shows the density and organic modifier of two types of nanoclays. All polymer materials and nanoclays were dried under vacuum for 12h at 100°C prior to melt processing. The nanoclays were ultrasonicated in acetone at various times between 1 and 4h and were dried in an oven. A weighed amount of nanoclay was mixed with the PET pellets using a twin-screw extruder (IMC-1969) and a batch mixer (IMC-1853) from Imoto Machinery. For the twin-screw extruder, compounding was carried out at a screw speed of 40rpm and extruder temperatures were held at 255, 255, 255 and 245°C from hopper to die. For the batch mixer, compounding was done at a temperature of 260°C with a rotor speed of 30rpm and 10min mixing time. The amount of nanoclay was varied from 2 to 10vol%.

Table 1: Density and organic modifier of two types of nanoclays

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Organic Modifier
DELLITE 43B	1.60	Dimethyl benzyl hydrogenated tallow ammonium
Cloisite 10A	1.69	

2.2 Testing methods

Dynamic viscoelastic tests were conducted in a SII Nanotechnology DMS 6100 in tension mode with an oscillatory frequency of 1Hz and a heating rate of 2°C/min. Three rectangular specimens of dimensions 45×5×0.5mm were tested in a temperature range of 20-100°C. A dynamic force of 50mN was used oscillating at fixed frequency. TEM was also used to examine the composite morphology at an acceleration voltage of 200kV. A TEM sample with about 50nm thickness was prepared by an ultramicrotome at room temperature. The morphology of ultrasonicated nanoclays was examined using SEM at an acceleration voltage of 5kV.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A Monte-Carlo algorithm implemented in the MacroPac program from Intelligensys was used to generate a unit cell with randomly distributed nanoclays. Fig. 1 shows a random unit cell of nanoclay/PET composites. Nanoclays are randomly placed into a PET matrix, with the restriction that they cannot overlap each other. Once the required volume fraction is achieved, the generation process of the unit cell is terminated. The nanoclay volume fraction is obtained as follows:

$$V_f = \frac{W^2 HN}{L^3} \quad (1)$$

where W is the width of a nanoclay, H is the thickness of a nanoclay, N is the number of nanoclays and L is the unit cell dimension. The linear elastic problem for the random unit cell model of

nanoclay/PET composites was solved using the Multiscale.Sim program implemented in the commercial finite element analysis code ANSYS. The composite Young's modulus (E_c) can be found by applying appropriate boundary conditions to the random unit cell model.

Fig. 1: Random unit cell model of nanoclay/PET composites

The individual materials are modeled as linear elastic and isotropic solids. For the PET matrix, the Young's modulus is measured to be 2.3GPa (storage modulus at 30°C) through the dynamic viscoelastic test and the Poisson's ratio is assumed to be 0.35, a typical value for polymer. For the nanoclay, the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are taken to be 178GPa and 0.2 [6, 7], respectively.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The storage modulus (E') and the loss modulus (E'') of the neat PET and the DELLITE 43B/EFG70 composites with different nanoclay volume fractions fabricated using the twin-screw extruder are plotted against temperature in Fig.2. It was observed that E' of the composite at 30°C increased with increasing the nanoclay volume fraction. As the temperature increased, the composites showed a gradual drop in E' . Moreover, E'' presented a peak above 60°C, which indicates a glass-to-rubbery transition in the polymer, i.e. the glass transition temperature (T_g). The composite with 2vol% nanoclay showed the highest T_g . This indicated that the nanoclay tend to restrict the mobility of the polymer chains in the matrix. However, as the nanoclay volume fraction increased from 2 to 10vol%, T_g of the composite decreased.

Fig. 2: The temperature dependence of the dynamic viscoelastic behavior of the neat PET and the nanoclay/PET composites containing different nanoclay volume fractions: (a) storage modulus; (b) loss modulus.

Fig.3 shows a TEM micrograph of the 5vol% Cloisite10A/EFG70 composite fabricated using the twin-screw extruder. In the TEM micrograph, the nanoclays appeared as dark areas and the plate like structure of the nanoclay can be clearly seen.

Fig.3: TEM Micrograph of the 5vol%Cloisite10A/EFG70 composite.

E' and E'' of the neat PET and the PET composites containing 5vol% nanoclays prepared at different ultrasonication time are plotted against temperature in Fig.4. These composites were fabricated using the batch mixer. At 30°C, E' of the composite increased as the ultrasonication time increased from 1 to 2h. Prolonged subjection to the ultrasonication beyond 2h showed a drop in E' of the composite. As the temperature increased, the composites showed a gradual drop in E' . Moreover, the increase in T_g is attained through the addition of the nanoclay. Moreover, T_g of the composite decreased with increasing ultrasonication time.

Fig.4 The temperature dependence of the dynamic viscoelastic behavior of the neat PET and the PET composites containing 5vol% nanoclays prepared at different ultrasonication time: (a) storage modulus; (b) loss modulus.

Fig.5 shows SEM images of as-received and ultrasonicated nanoclays (Cloisite 10A). The SEM image of as-received nanoclays illustrates sphere-like particles. The morphology of ultrasonicated nanoclays reveals the substantial changes induced by the ultrasonication process. The ultrasonicated nanoclays exist as flake-like grains and platelets. This indicates that the breaking and delamination of the nanoclay occurs during ultrasonication process.

(a)

(b)

Fig.5 SEM images of nanoclays (Cloisite 10A): (a) as-received nanoclay; (b) ultrasonicated nanoclay (4h).

From the TEM observation, W is taken to be $3\mu\text{m}$ and calculations were carried out. Fig.6 shows the Young's moduli obtained from numerical simulations and dynamic viscoelastic tests (storage modulus at 30°C) versus V_f . E_c of the composites with $H = 0.5\mu\text{m}$ increased with increasing V_f . The difference between the model and the experiments is most likely caused by the fact that while the model assumes that the nanoclays are perfectly dispersed in the PET matrix, a significant amount of undispersed nanoclays forming clusters remains in the composite material.

Fig.6 Young's moduli obtained from numerical simulations and dynamic viscoelastic tests versus nanoclay volume fraction.

Effect of H on E_c of the composites with $V_f=5\text{vol}\%$ is presented in Fig.7. E_c increased with decreasing H . Below $H=0.25\mu\text{m}$, the effect of H on E_c became stronger. The thickness of the nanoclays depends upon how well they are intercalated and exfoliated. To obtain enhanced composite Young's modulus, high degree of intercalation and exfoliation is desired.

Fig.7 Predicted Young's modulus of 5vol%nanoclay/PET composites versus nanoclay thickness

5 CONCLUSIONS

Nanoclay/PET composites were prepared by ultrasonication and melt processing. The effects of ultrasonication time and nanoclay volume fraction on the temperature dependence of the dynamic viscoelastic properties of nanoclay/PET composites were examined. Moreover, the three-dimensional unit cell model was used in finite element analysis to determine the effective Young's modulus of nanoclay/PET composites. Based on the experimental and analytical results, the following conclusions are reached:

- (1) By increasing the nanoclay volume fraction, the storage modulus of the nanoclay/PET composites at 30°C increased and the glass transition temperature of the nanoclay/PET composites decreased.
- (2) The storage modulus at 30°C and the glass transition temperature of the nanoclay/PET composites were influenced by the ultrasonication time.
- (3) The morphology of nanoclays significantly changed via ultrasonication process. Ultrasonication would induce the better dispersion and exfoliation of the nanoclay.
- (4) The predicted Young's modulus of the nanoclay/PET composites was strongly affected by change in nanoclay thickness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Adaptable and Seamless Technology Transfer Program funded by Japan Science and Technology Agency (No.231Z02468), and the research grants from the Hokuriku Industrial Advancement Center and the Toyama Prefectural University.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.S. Solis, A.G. Rejon and O. Manero, Production of nanocomposites of PET-Montmorillonite clay by an extrusion process, *Macromolecular Symposia*, **192**, 2003, pp. 281-292 (doi:10.1002/masy.200390038).
- [2] G.D. Barber, B.H. Calhoun and R.B. Moore, Poly(ethylene terephthalate) ionomer based clay nanocomposites produced via melt extrusion, *Polymer*, **46**, 2005, pp. 6706-6714 (doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2005.05.024).

- [3] A. Ammala, C. Bell and K. Dean, Poly(ethylene terephthalate) clay nanocomposites: Improved dispersion based on an aqueous ionomer, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1328-1337 (doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.12.012).
- [4] C.P. McAdam, N.E. Hudson, J.J. Liggat and R.A. Pethrick, Synthesis and characterization of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites prepared by ultrasonication and in situ polymerization, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **108**, 2008, pp. 2242-2251 (doi: 10.1002/app.25599).
- [5] M.A. Tarawneh, S.H. Ahmad, R. Rasid, S.Y. Yahya and S.Y.E. Noum, The enhancement of properties of TPNR/clay nanocomposites using ultrasonic treatment, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **30**, 2011, pp. 524-532 (doi: 10.1177/0731684411399134).
- [6] J. Wang and R. Pyrz, Prediction of the overall moduli of layered silicate-reinforced nanocomposites-part II: analyses, *Composites Science and Technology*, **64**, 2004, pp. 935-944 (doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(03)00025-3).
- [7] F. Bédoui and L. Cauvin, Elastic properties prediction of nano-clay reinforced polymers using hybrid micromechanical models, *Computational Materials Science*, **65**, 2012, pp.309-314 (doi: 10.1016/j.commatsci.2012.07.023).